

Identifiable Dimensions of Collaborative Learning (Peer Teaching and Problem-Based Learning) on the Academic Outcomes of Business Education Students in Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study considered a correlational study between identifiable dimensions of collaborative learning (peer teaching and problem-based learning) on the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State. Two research questions were answered and two null hypotheses were tested in the study. The correlational design was adopted for the study. The population was made up of 1,847 business education students in five Tertiary institutions: one federal owned institution and four state owned institutions that run business education programme. In determining the sample size of 369 for the study, the Taro-Yamene (1964) formula for finite population was applied. The research instrument used for data collection is the structured questionnaire of four-point likert rating scale. The Instrument was face and content validated. The Cronbach Alpha Reliability Test (CART) technique was adopted to obtain a coefficient of 0.87. The data that were gathered in the course of this study were analyzed using relevant descriptive statistics which included mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while F-Statistics was obtained from the simple regression estimation which was conducted alongside the descriptive statistics for the hypotheses. It was found out that, there is a significant relationship between identifiable dimensions of collaborative learning (peer teaching and problem-based learning) on the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State. Amongst others, it was recommended that Efforts should be made by business education lecturers to incorporate the collaborative learning models to their respective teaching approaches when engaging business education students in their academic endeavours.

Keywords: Collaborative Learning, Peer Teaching, Problem Based Learning, Academic Outcomes & Business Education

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

At the international community, the business environment has over time undergone continuous and constant changes in the area of technology and culture and these changes have equally changed the way students are being educated. Better ways of teaching and learning have evolved over time. One of these modern methods of teaching is the collaborative learning method (Pozzi et al., 2023). Collaborative learning model like other experiential methods such as guest lecturers, live projects, internships, games, case research, action research and customized business simulations has been found to contribute immensely to students' creativity and development of employability skills (Global Business School Network, 2017). In teamwork and decision –making course teaching, Zieba and Zieba (2014) proposed a problem-solving approach to create learning environment where students are encumbered with problematic task to perform. First and foremost, students solve it independently and after making specific related actions the participating students are organized into teams to work out a mutually accepted strategy of solution. The central objective of this instructional approach is aimed to determine the quality of teamwork and evaluate the extent team synergy, understanding the dominant culture and differences in individual work in comparison to team collaboration.

Collaborative learning is a sustained, two-way communication between students and students or between students and the coordinating educator, tutor, lecturer or facilitator with the central objective to complete task or build social relationship. The web-based learning environment has been split into four fundamental types; the learner-content, learner-learner, learner-instructor and learner –interface which create an effective environment for information sharing, negotiation and knowledge construction. The various components of interactive collaboration pedagogy except learner-interface interaction have been related to cognitive and social constructivist orientations. The socio-constructivist perspective is rooted in the argument that knowledge is collaboratively constructed through social context mediated by discourse.

The main goal of collaborative learning in the classroom is to influence the information and abilities needed to fulfill both academic goals and financial responsibilities in any organization, commercial or otherwise (Olorode & Jimoh, 2016). Business education is a special discipline that equips students with the knowledge, abilities, and attitudes needed to manage advanced office equipment and information. Nwazor (2012), however, has criticized the lack of the education provided by tertiary institutions, particularly in the business education programmes; as students have not been efficiently prepared for situations they will face in the real world after graduation. Igberaharha (2021) noted that, education plays a significant role in the foundations of the economic, social, cultural, and political development of any nation. The perceived expectation gap between the knowledge acquired by students during their undergraduate programmes and what is expected of them upon graduation is traceable to the mode of teaching and learning adopted by most tertiary institutions in Nigeria and beyond. Hence, collaborative learning could have a correlation on business education student's outcome.

Statement of The Problem

The conventional teaching strategy, also known as the traditional "chalk and talk" method of teaching, which was consistently used by business education lecturers at the tertiary level, is gradually not yielding much as it concerns business education students' academic performances. According to proponents of modern teaching techniques like the collaborative learning model, more notable results are produced using these modern teaching techniques (Tumba, Chinda, & Andeyarka, 2014). However, in recent years, this argument has caused a lot of concern about collaborative learning (Nwosu & Akaraka, 2020; Ikpesu, 2021).

Despite the aforementioned, a close examination of the results of earlier studies reveals that, despite growing concerns about collaborative learning, previous attention has not been given to analyzing the impact that particular forms of collaborative learning may have on students' identifiable academic outcomes, as demonstrated by business education students. Also, instruction does not fully acknowledge the new age environment in classrooms in terms of constructivist learning. There is avalanche of empirical evidence on the presumed importance of collaborative learning methodologies; however, there is dearth of empirical evidence on how peer teaching and problem-based learning impacts academic outcomes of students particularly, Business Education Students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Hence, the paper considered a correlational study between identifiable dimensions of collaborative learning (peer teaching and problem-based learning) on the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Objectives of The Study

The main focus of this research was to examine a correlational study between identifiable dimensions of collaborative learning (peer teaching and problem-based learning) on the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State. The specific objectives were to:

1. Examine the relationship between collaborative learning dimension of peer teaching and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State.
2. Examine the relationship between collaborative learning dimension of problem-based learning and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Research Questions

In line with the objectives of study, the following research questions were raised and answered:

1. Is there any significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of peer teaching and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State?
2. Is there any significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of problem-based learning and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of peer teaching and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State.

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H02: There is no significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of problem-based learning and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The related literature was reviewed under the following sub headings; concept of collaborative learning; dimensions of collaborative learning (peer teaching and problem-based learning); collaborative learning and academic outcomes.

Concept of Collaborative Learning

Collaborative learning is a cognitively engaged learning that focus on the process of building knowledge through a combination of comprehending and transforming experiences of participants. The method supplemented by tools and technology produces a learning environment that sparks students' interaction and cognitive engagement. Accordingly, Sheriff, Ifedayo & Yetunde (2019) argues that collaborative learning is facilitated by multimedia instructional technology so that lecturers and students alike who work together to accomplish certain learning objectives create a synergy.

Under the collaborative learning model, lecturers and students work together in groups or in teams to encourage engagements and interactions. To fulfill the learning needs of the current generation of students generally, collaborative learning has recently undergone extensive adaptation to the more dynamic corporate and educational environments (Ikpesu, 2021). With little teacher interaction or direction, students work collaboratively to exchange ideas and information in a system of learning known as collaborative teaching. As a result, it is a teaching style that encourages discussion among students in the same class and age group. A problem-solving, task-completion, or product-creation activity is completed by a group of learners as part of the collaborative learning approach to teaching and learning. It is a method of instruction whereby students cooperate in small groups to achieve a common objective.

Dimensions of Collaborative Learning Used in the Study

The dimensions of collaborative learning used for this study and which literatures were reviewed on are peer teaching and problem-based learning:

Peer Teaching

Peer teaching is a form of collaborative learning where under given arrangements, students intentionally teach themselves. A key element of effective university classrooms is student participation in the learning process. Too frequently, we find students enter a class, sit down, listen to a lecture, and then leave without using higher-order thinking skills. During lectures, most students are typically uninterested, detached, and cognitively disengaged (Pozzi, et al., 2023).

Practically, peer teaching offers participants to act as both teachers and students in a combination of techniques. In most cases, participating students collaborate with each other one-on-one while studying. Students who participate as "teachers" at any given time typically follow instructions for what to say and how to interact with their counterparts who are participating as "learners." The benefit of peer teaching is that it allows participating students/collaborators to tailor lessons to each student's needs. In many instances, all students taking part in peer teaching/tutoring get to act as both teachers and students. Peer tutoring has been shown to have a wide range of positive outcomes, including improvements in reading,

language skills, academic success, student attitudes toward school, and classroom behavior (Insai & Poonlap, 2010).

Problem-Based Learning

The protocols for small-group discussions are created to encourage students to use critical thinking skills such as interpreting, evaluating, analyzing, and/or synthesizing knowledge and concepts. Students are required to think critically, add their ideas to the topic, listen intently, and answer meaningfully to one another in the small-group environment and structured discussion format.

Problem Based Learning (PBL) students engage in groups to assess their prior knowledge, consider what they need to learn, consider what they should do, consider how and where to get new information, and then work to solve a problem. Students will develop hypotheses, recognize learning difficulties, search out information sources, and assess the knowledge they find, reflect, incorporate new information, and synthesize solutions to obstacles. Teachers can help students learn by encouraging them to concentrate on their learning goals, providing a conducive learning atmosphere, and keeping an eye on the learning process (Kumar, 2017). PBL is an inductive process, which is considered a better alternative to traditional teaching methods in both secondary and higher education, and a key area of study for educational scholars in the twenty-first century.

In higher institutions, educational issues may be resolved in a problem-based collaborative learning setting. This is so that students can put out effort to find solutions to real problems in a problem-based collaborative learning environment, use various technology tools to identify the relevant sources, collaborate with classmates, receive instructor support, and develop a solution.

Collaborative Learning and Academic Outcomes

Over the past decades, educators have understood the benefits of group learning. There is widespread agreement among educators that pupils learn poorly when they are treated as lone "receivers" of information. In fact, overcoming isolation is a necessary part of learning to write. In order to promote active learning and give students the chance to become more deeply involved with their writing and with one another, collaborative learning exercises, such as peer review workshops, collaborative research assignments, group presentations, collaborative papers, and discussion groups, are essential elements in enhancing classroom learning (Mohammad, 2015).

Academic outcomes can be measured on the basis of the breadth of knowledge gained via learning. The child learns by following the directions they are given at schools, which are structured around a number of core activities in which teachers assign students tasks and assess and contrast the caliber of their work. More achievement opportunities are offered by the school than by the household so that researches have established that a variety of variables, in addition to knowledge, affect students' academic performance (Kumar, 2017). In most cases, an understanding of the academic outcomes of students are well captured by a careful analysis of the extent of their being active, being proficient, having an effect on the surroundings, and competing against some benchmark of excellence in the area of their academics. Prior studies preferred the word "academic success" and/or academic performance and are mostly used interchangeably. Notwithstanding, the concept "academic outcomes" is more encompassing as it covers both measurable and observable/qualitative attributes.

Noteworthy, the academic performance of students is one of the performance indicators for any educational institution as it summarizes the students' capacity to demonstrate academic

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success in the accomplishment of desired objectives. Although many academics stress the need of mental and cognitive ability for academic success, great intellect does not ensure it, and people should be aware of their preferred learning techniques. It is in this light that this study examined the extent of influence which collaborative learning has on the academic/learning outcomes of business education students.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The correlational research design which is structured for establishing relationship between two or more variables was adopted in this study. The study established the relationship between collaborative learning dimensions (peer teaching and problem-based learning) and the academic outcomes of Business Education Students. The independent variables of collaborative learning are peer teaching and problem-based learning, while the dependent variable is academic outcomes.

Population of the Study

The population of the study was 1,847 business education students in five Tertiary institutions in Delta State Nigeria: one federal owned institution and four state owned institutions that run business education programme. They are: Delta State University, Abraka (371); University of Delta, Agbor (377); College of Education Warri (343), College of Education, Mosogar (320), and Federal College of Education (T), Asaba (436) in 2021/2022 academic session. (Source: Admission units in the various institutions; 2023).

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

In determining the sample size for the study, the Taro-Yamene (1964) formula for finite population was applied. The formula was considered more appropriate since the population of respondents is large and known (Eric, 2009). 20% of the population from various institutions were used to yield a sample size of: Delta State University, Abraka (74); University of Delta, Agbor (75); College of Education Warri (69), College of Education, Mosogar (64), and Federal College of Education (T), Asaba (87). This gave a total sample size of 369.

Instrument

A well-structured questionnaire was used to elicit responses from the sampled students in the course of this study. The questionnaire is divided into two parts. Part A was designed to obtain demographic information about the respondents. Part B was designed using the four point-like scale to obtain responses relating to the research questions and specific objectives on peer teaching and problem-based learning. While their Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) was obtained and used as their academic outcomes.

Validity of Instrument

Two types of procedure were adopted by the researchers for this study to establish the validity of the instrument. These are the face validity and the content validity.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was established through the Cronbach Alpha Reliability Test (CART) technique. In order to get the relevant data for this purpose, a pilot study was

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conducted and draft copy of the questionnaire was administered to fifty (50) business education students in the Delta State University Affiliate programme of Michael and Cecelia Ibru University, Agbarotor. The overall CART coefficient stood at 0.8653 (approximately 0.87), showing that the research instrument is reliable. The choice of Cronbach Alpha’s reliability was based on the fact that: the questionnaire items are of multiple response type.

Method of Data Collection

Data were obtained through the use of self-administered questionnaire to the respondents in order to obtain the dimensions of Collaborative learning (peer teaching and problem-based learning). While their Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) was obtained and used as their academic outcomes.

Method of Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using relevant descriptive statistics which included mean and standard deviation. To test the relevant hypotheses, the F-Statistics was obtained from the simple regression estimation which was conducted alongside the descriptive statistics. The results from both the descriptive and inferential statistics were however presented by means of relevant tables.

Data Presentation

Research Question One: Is there any significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of peer teaching and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State?

Table 1
Responses to Items on Collaborative Learning Dimension of Peer Teaching (CLDPT) on the Academic Outcomes of Business Education Students

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Mean	Std. Dev	Remarks
CLDPT1	Peer teaching enhances the academic outcomes of business education students	3.52	0.768	Strongly Agree
CLDPT2	Business education students learn better when they teach themselves	3.51	0.761	Strongly Agree
CLDPT3	Peer teaching gives students the opportunities of sharing their ideas and interact with others while learning	3.51	0.701	Strongly Agree
CLDPT4	Students are more active and adapts faster when applying the peer teaching dimension of collaborative learning	3.50	0.694	Strongly Agree
CLDPT5	Involvement in students teaching students has positively influenced the	3.50	0.754	Strongly Agree

academic outcome of business education students.				
GRAND MEAN	3.51	0.736	Strongly Agree	

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2023.

Table 2

Summary of Pearson's product moment correlation co-efficient (r) computation for Collaborative Learning Dimension of Peer Teaching (CLDPT) and the Academic Outcomes of Business Education Students

Variables	N	ΣX /ΣY	ΣX ² /ΣY ²	Grand Mean	ΣXY	R
Peer Teaching (X)	369	630.85	2345.9	3.51	1568.67	0.70
Academic Outcome (Y)	369	414.11	1215.52	3.56		

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2023

In order to answer research question one, a Pearson's product moment Correlation co-efficient (r) was computed using the variables of peer teaching and students' academic outcome. The summary of the result generated as indicated in table 2 above, shows that the grand mean for peer teaching (3.51) is lower than the grand mean of their academic outcome (3.56) and that there is a positive correlation between student's peer teaching and their academic outcome (r = 0.70). The answer to research question 1 therefore, is that peer teaching has relationship on students' academic outcome in Business education.

Research Question Two: Is there any significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of problem-based learning and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State?

Table 3

Perception of Respondents on Collaborative Learning Dimension of Problem Based Learning Teaching (CLDPBL) on the Academic Outcomes of Business Education Students

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Mean	Std. Dev	Remarks
CLDPBL 1	Involvement of students in Problem based learning has significant positive influence on examination outcomes of business education students	3.64	0.755	Strongly Agree
CLDPBL 2	Students who partake in Problem based learning tend to have more understanding of the subject and subsequently perform excellently during examination	3.54	0.723	Strongly Agree

CLDPBL 3	Being part of Problem based learning has positively influenced learning and students' performance during examinations	3.51	0.693	Strongly Agree
CLDPBL 4	PBL students engage in groups to assess their prior knowledge, and considers what they need to learn which influences business education student's outcome.	3.67	0.671	Strongly Agree
CLDPBL 5	Problem based learning has particularly contributed to improvement in learning and examination outcomes of business education students	3.73	0.663	Strongly Agree
GRAND MEAN		3.62	0.701	Strongly Agree

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2023

Table 4

Summary of Pearson's product moment correlation co-efficient (r) computation for Collaborative Learning Dimension of Problem Based Learning (CLDPBL) and the Academic Outcomes of Business Education Students

Variables	N	$\Sigma X / \Sigma Y$	$\Sigma X^2 / \Sigma Y^2$	Grand Mean	ΣXY	R
Peer Based Learning (X)	369	634.87	2342.6	3.62	1572.67	0.68
Academic Outcome (Y)	369	414.11	1215.52	3.56		

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2023

In order to answer research question two, a Pearson's product moment Correlation co-efficient (r) was computed using the variables of problem-based learning and students' academic outcome. The summary of the result generated as indicated in table 4 above, shows that the grand mean for problem-based learning (3.62) is higher than the grand mean of their academic outcome (3.56) and that there is a positive correlation between student's peer teaching and their academic outcome (r = 0.68). The answer to research question 2 therefore, is that problem-based learning has relationship on students' academic outcome in Business education.

Hypothesis I: There is no significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of peer teaching and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Table 5

Model Summary Relationship between Collaborative Learning Dimension of Peer Teaching and the Academic Outcomes of Business education students

Academic Outcomes	Coeff.	Std. Err.	T	P > t	R ²	Decision
Peer Teaching	0.8749	0.0305	28.71	0.000	0.8191	Reject Null
_cons	0.5356	0.1087	4.93	0.000		
F(1, 367)	824.28					
Prob > F	0.0000					
No. of Obs.	369					

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2023

Table 5 presents the result for the test of hypothesis 1 of this study. As observed, the correlation between collaborative learning collaborative learning dimension of peer teaching and the academic outcomes is positive (0.8749). The standard error obtained is 0.0305 indicating that the model estimating the extent to which peer teaching influences academic outcome\s is approximately 99.97% accurate since the distance between data points and fitted values of the regression model is averagely small (0.0305). The result of the t-statistics which is 28.71 with is corresponding p-value of 0.000 suggests that the general belief of the respondents is that there is a significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of peer teaching and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State. This position is further confirmed by the result of the F-statistics of 824.28 (Prob > F = 0.000). Overall, going by the result of the F-Statistics, the null hypothesis 1 of this study is rejected. We therefore accept the alternate hypothesis thus implying that there is a significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of peer teaching and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Hypotheses II: There is no significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of problem-based learning and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Table 6: Model Summary Relationship between Collaborative Learning Dimension of Problem Based Learning and the Academic Outcomes of Business education students

Academic Outcomes	Coeff.	Std. Err.	T	P > t	R ²	Decision
Problem Based Learning	0.7739	0.0413	18.75	0.000	0.6588	Reject Null
_cons	1.0533	0.1472	7.16	0.000		
F(1, 367)	351.41					
Prob > F	0.0000					
No. of Obs.	369					

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2023

Table 6 presents the result for the test of hypothesis II of this study. Noticeably, the correlation between collaborative learning dimension of problem based learning and the academic outcomes of business education students is positive (0.7739). The import of this is that problem-based learning is positively related to the academic outcomes of students so that an increase in the level of involvement of students in collaborative learning will result to an increase in the level of improvement in the academics of students. The standard error obtained is 0.0413 indicating that the model estimating the extent to which collaborative learning dimension of problem-based learning influences the academic outcomes of business education students is approximately 99.96% accurate since the distance between data points and fitted values of the regression model is averagely small (0.0413). The result of the t-statistics which is 18.75 with is corresponding p-value of 0.000 suggests that the general belief of the respondents is that collaborative learning dimension of problem-based learning has significant influence on the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State. This position is further confirmed by the result of the F-statistics of 351.41 (Prob > F = 0.000). Overall, going by the result of the F-Statistics, the null hypothesis II of this study is rejected. We therefore accept the alternate hypothesis thus implying that there is a significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of problem-based learning and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Discussion of Findings

This study considered a correlational study between identifiable dimensions of collaborative learning (peer teaching and problem-based learning) on the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State.

First, from the computed mean values and their respected standard deviations, we observed that majority of respondents strongly agree with the assertion that there is a significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of peer teaching and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State. Students prefer to collaborate with their peers for several reasons which ranges from writing of assignments, sharing of ideas, active interaction with their peers, and speedy adaptation to topical discussion amongst others. Studies (Al-kaabi, 2016; Nwosu & Akaraka, 2020) have shown that collaborative learning offers more opportunities to students when compared with the classroom methodology, making collaborative learning more complaint with recent technologies of learning. Oroka, Atarere and Okifo (2020) noted that significant advances in quality and the application of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have become so attached to contemporary educational delivery globally.

From the result of the test of Hypothesis I, most of the respondents believes that there is a significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of peer teaching and the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State. This position justifies why Ikpesu (2021) argued that in order to fulfill the learning needs of the current generation of students generally, collaborative learning has recently undergone extensive adaptation to the more dynamic corporate and educational environments. It is pertinent to note that our finding corroborates the position of prior documentary evidence, though, outside Nigeria (Bicen & zdamli, 2011).

In addition, from the results of research question two and hypothesis two majority of respondents strongly agree with the assertion that there is a significant relationship between collaborative learning dimension of problem based learning and the academic outcomes of

business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta This position justifies why previous research evidence had argued that collaborative learning engenders interactive processes of discussion, negotiation and information sharing with co-participants; produces better academic outcomes when properly synthesized (Chandra, 2015).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, scholars and researches have thus maintained that better ways of teaching and learning have evolved over time (Pozzi, 2023). With this thought, it becomes important to seek strategies that will employ approaches suitable for enhancing better academic performance of students generally and business education students in particular. Interestingly, collaborative learning offers great opportunities to students' creativity and development of employability skills achievement. It was thus concluded that there is a significant relationship between identifiable dimensions of collaborative learning (peer teaching and problem-based learning) on the academic outcomes of business education students among tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Recommendations

In the light of the results of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Efforts should be made by business education lecturers to incorporate the collaborative learning models to their respective teaching approaches when engaging business education students in their academic endeavours.
2. To sustain the present perception of business education students that peer teaching significantly influences academic outcomes of students. Business education students should be encouraged to be actively involved in collaborative groups among their peers
3. Students at all levels should be encouraged to get themselves engaged in various forms of collaborative models and particularly, problem-based learning which has proven to be one important method of collaboration that has improved the intellectual capacity and learning skills of students.

References

- Al-kaabi, A. F. (2016). Effects of collaborative learning on the achievement of students with different learning styles at Qatar University (QU). *A Thesis submitted for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy, College of Business, Arts and Social Sciences Department of Education, Brunel University, London*. November
- Bicen, H. & Özdamlı, F. (2011). Validating the instrument of web-based collaborative learning competencies using factor analysis. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 15 (1) 3921 – 3926
- Bower, M. & Richards, D. (2006) 'Collaborative learning: Some possibilities and limitations for students and teachers', In *Proceedings of the Conference for the Australasian Society for Computers in Learning in Tertiary Education (ASCILITE'06)*, *ACM Transactions on Computing Education*, 9 (1), 79-89.
- Chandra, R. (2015). Collaborative Learning for Educational Achievement. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)*, 5(2), 1-4.
- Global Business School Network (2017). Business education should focus on relevance. <https://gbsn.org>
- Insai, S. & Poonlap T. (2017). More heads are better than one: Peer editing in a translation classroom of EFL learners, *PASAA*, 54(1), 82-107.
- Igberaharha, O. C. (2021). Improving the Quality of Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) for Sustainable Growth and Development of Nigeria. *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*. 8 (1), 109-115.
- Ikpesu, O. C. (2021). Collaborative learning model and business education students' active engagement in Rivers State Universities. *Rivers State University Journal of Education (RSUJOE)*, 24(2), 76-85
- Kumar, R. (2017). The Effect of collaborative learning on enhancing student achievement: A meta-analysis. *A Thesis in The Department of Education Presented in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Degree of Master of Arts (Educational Technology) at Concordia University Montreal, Quebec, Canada*
- Mohammad, A. (2015). Experimental methods of teaching business studies: Practical approaches beyond lecturing. *International Journal of Core Engineering and Management*, 1, 59-73
- Nwazor, J. C. (2012). Capacity building, entrepreneurship and sustainable development. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies (JETERAPS)*, 3 (1), 51-54.

- Nwosu, A. N. & Akaraka, O. E. (2020). Collaborative learning approaches as innovative strategies required for equipping business education students for global outlook, *Nigerian Journal of Business Education (NIGJBED)*, 7(2), 92-110
- Olorode, J. & Jimoh, A. (2016). Effectiveness of guided discovery learning strategy and gender sensitivity on students' academic. *International Journal of Academic Research*, 6(4), 182-189.
- Oroka, O. V.; Atarere, L. O. & Okifo, J. (2020). Reinventing Business Education through Quality and Information Communication Technology (ICT) for Global Competitiveness among Selected Universities in South-South and South-East Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Information Systems & Technology Research*. 8 (4), 32-43.
- Pozzi, F., Manganello, F., & Persico, D. (2023). Collaborative learning: A Design Challenge for Teachers. *Education Sciences* 13(4), 331-340.
- Sheriff, A. A.; Ifedayo, O. A. & yetunde, T. O. (2019). Collaborative learning method: Effects of ability levels and school type on the junior secondary students' business studies achievement in Edo State. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 6(1), 198 – 207.
- Tumba, O. Chinda, C. & Andeyarka, P. (2014). Comparative Effects of Teaching Methods Used for Teaching Skills in Radio Television and Electronics Servicing Trade. *American International Journal of Social Science*, 3(4), 121-125.
- Zieba, M. & Zieba K. (2014). *Innovative approaches to business education*. Via University College, Demark.